

CLINICAL TRIAL PROTOCOL

Supportive Care and Antibiotics for Severe Pneumonia among Hospitalised Children (SEARCH): A Pragmatic Randomised Controlled Trial

GENERAL INFORMATION

Trial Registration Number:	Clinical Trials.gov NCT04041791
Funder:	Joint Global Health Trials Scheme of the UK Department for International Development (DFID), the National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) the UK Medical Research Council (MRC), and the Wellcome Trust
Sponsor	University of Oxford Research Governance Ethics and Assurance

CONTENTS

1.	LAY SUMMARY.....	4
2.	LIST OF INVESTIGATORS.....	7
3.	ABSTRACT.....	9
4.	INTRODUCTION.....	10
5.	TRIAL OBJECTIVES AND PURPOSE.....	16
6.	TRIAL DESIGN.....	17
7.	SELECTION OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS.....	18
8.	WITHDRAWAL OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS	22
9.	TREATMENT OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS	22
10.	ASSESSMENT OF SAFETY	28
11.	PROTOCOL DEVIATIONS.....	31
12.	QUALITY CONTROL AND QUALITY ASSURANCE.....	32
13.	DATA MANAGEMENT	33
14.	STATISTICAL CONSIDERATIONS.....	34
15.	INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY	36
16.	TIME FRAME FOR THE TRIAL	37
17.	ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS.....	37
18.	DATA SHARING.....	41
19.	ARCHIVING AND RECORD RETENTION	41
20.	FINANCING AND INSURANCE	41
21.	TRIAL MANAGEMENT	42
22.	TRAINING AND SETTING UP.....	42
23.	REPORTING, DISSEMINATION AND NOTIFICATION OF RESULTS.....	43
24.	REFERENCES.....	44
25.	APPENDICES	49

GLOSSARY OF TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS:

AE	Adverse event
CGMR-C	Centre for Geographic Medicine Research – Coast, Kilifi, Kenya
CRF	Case Report Form
CSC	Centre Scientific Committee
DSMB	Data & Safety Monitoring Board
GMP	Good manufacturing practice
ICF	Information and consent form
IP	Investigational product
KEMRI	Kenya Medical Research Institute
KWTRP	KEMRI/Wellcome Trust Research Programme, Kilifi, Kenya
NQCL	National Quality Control Laboratory, Kenya
PPB-ECCT	Pharmacy & Poisons Board Expert Committee on Clinical Trials
OXTREC	Oxford Tropical Research Ethics Committee
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
SAE	Serious adverse event
SERU	KEMRI Scientific and Ethics Review Unit, Nairobi
SOP	Standard of operating procedure
SUSAR	Serious Unexpected Suspected Adverse Reaction
UNICEF	United Nations Children’s Fund
WHO	World Health Organisation

1. LAY SUMMARY

Formal Title

Supportive care and antibiotics for severe pneumonia among hospitalised children

Lay Title

A study to compare different injectable antibiotic treatments and different modes of fluid treatment for children with severe pneumonia.

What is the problem?

Pneumonia, an infection of the lungs, is one of the leading causes of death among young children. World Health Organization (WHO) has recommendations for the diagnosis and treatment of pneumonia in low- and middle-income countries using simple clinical features and low cost, widely available antibiotics. The recommend treatment for children at the highest risk of death (severe pneumonia) is injectable benzyl penicillin or ampicillin and gentamicin. Following the introduction of vaccines against the main causes of pneumonia to national immunisation programmes in many low-income countries, there has been growing debate over the appropriateness of the currently recommended treatments. Many clinicians already believe that the recommended treatment is ineffective and frequently opt to use other antibiotics such as amoxicillin-clavulanic acid and ceftriaxone instead. We need a study to determine which antibiotics are best.

Children with severe pneumonia are typically not able to eat food and so standard practice is to try and continue some form of fluid and energy intake during the serious illness. Some authorities advise against feeding through a tube inserted into the stomach through the nose in severely ill children. The main reason for this is are the potential for affecting the ability to breath in a patient already experiencing difficulty breathing and an increased risk of choking on feeds given through the tube. However, the alternative, providing fluids through an intravenous drip, requires careful monitoring by a nurse to ensure the fluid is given at a safe rate over the desired duration. If fluids drip in too fast this may itself cause breathing problems. This a common challenge in many low resource settings where a limited number of nursing staff are required to attend to several duties. Fluids provided through a drip also lack the necessary nutrients to match the increased demands of the body during a serious illness. We plan to carry out a study comparing the different antibiotics and approaches to feeding/fluid management described above.

What questions are we trying to answer?

Current data suggest that more than 10% of children with severe pneumonia die and we are trying to find better ways of treating them to reduce this. We want to find out (1) which antibiotics are the most effective for the treatment of children admitted to hospital with severe pneumonia, and (2) whether feeding through a tube inserted into the stomach through the nose is more effective than providing fluids through a drip inserted in a vein for the management of children with severe pneumonia.

Where is the study taking place, how many people does it involve and how are they selected?

The study will take place at up to 10 hospitals in Kenya, one in Uganda and one in Tanzania. A total of 4392 children aged 2 – 59 months will be allocated to the study treatment groups through a balanced process that ensures each child has a fair chance of receiving any given study treatments. Each of the two questions will be studied in the same set of patients. Thus, a child recruited in the study will receive any one of the three antibiotic treatments and either an intravenous drip for fluids or tube feeding into the stomach. For each of the study questions, we will compare the percentage of children who die within the first five days of recruitment in the alternative treatment groups. We will also compare the length of hospitalisation, time taken to be able to drink, any adverse effects that may be related to the antibiotic treatments, and the percentage of children who die within 30 days of recruitment in the different treatment groups. In a smaller group of children at selected sites, we will also study the causes of pneumonia by performing chest X-rays and studying samples collected from the nose, and the long-term outcomes of the illness by assessing the same group of children 3 months after recruitment.

What does the study involve for those who are in it?

A member of the study team will seek initial permission from the caregiver to include their child in the study. This initial permission will allow children to be provisionally enrolled into the study without delaying the initiation of emergency treatment. The study clinician will interview the caregiver and examine each child after which he/she will prescribe one of the three antibiotic treatments and either an intravenous fluid drip or tube feeding, allocated through a random process. Children will be reviewed daily by the study team, working together with the hospital staff to provide the best care available in the hospital. Further detailed written permission will be sought by the study clinician once the child has stabilised during which additional information on the study will be provided. Children will be followed up during the hospital stay and for 30 days after enrolment through a phone call or a face-to-face visit at the hospital, depending on the alternative that is more convenient and feasible for the caregiver.

We will perform a chest X-ray and collect a sample from the nose in a small group of patients who will be followed up for three months after enrolment to better understand the causes and long-term effects of severe pneumonia.

What are the benefits and risks/costs of the study for those involved?

The antibiotics that will be given in the study are already regularly used routinely in hospitals and the doctor in charge of the care for children in the hospital (not the study doctor) will be able to alter the treatment they receive if they feel it is in the child's best interest. Some of the side effects that have been associated with them include: loss of appetite, stomach discomfort, diarrhoea, vomiting, skin rash and very rarely an allergic reaction. Some pain and discomfort will be experienced from the initial injection used to insert the drip that will then be used to give the antibiotics and intravenous fluids but this is a common part of existing practice. There is also a small risk of bruising, infection or leakage of the drip at the site of injection. Children who are assigned to receive feeds through a tube in the nose may experience discomfort during insertion of the tube but this is also a common part of existing practice. There is a small risk of the tube being placed in the wrong location or displaced resulting in choking. Children who are selected for collection of samples from the nose may experience brief discomfort during the procedure. The injection/drip insertion and administration of intravenous treatments, feeding tube insertion and checking for position before each use and collection of samples from the nose will all be done by experienced healthcare professionals, following the study protocols for these procedures. Parents/guardians of patients who we are unable to contact via telephone will be requested to return to the hospital on a specified date at least 30 days after enrolment with their children. Reimbursement for out-of-pocket costs associated with taking part will be provided at each scheduled visit, based on KEMRI Wellcome Trust Research Programme guidelines.

How will the study benefit society?

Since pneumonia is the leading cause of hospitalisation in Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, and other countries in the region, the findings from this research will directly inform policy on the appropriate care of a substantial number of sick children with the hope of reducing child mortality.

When does the study start and finish?

The study aims to start as soon as ethical approval is obtained. Recruitment of participants is expected to continue for about two years. We expect to report the final results within one year of competing follow up of the final study participant.

2. LIST OF INVESTIGATORS

Dr Ambrose Agweyu (PI)	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme / University of Oxford
Prof Mike English	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme / University of Oxford
Prof Elizabeth Maleche Obimbo	University of Nairobi
Prof Elizabeth Allen	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, UK
Dr Charles Opondo	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, UK
Dr Adolfine Hokororo	Bugando Medical Centre, Tanzania
Dr Emmanuel Tenywa	Jinja Regional Referral Hospital, Uganda
Dr Samuel Akech	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme / University of Oxford
Prof Grace Irimu	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme / University of Nairobi
Prof James Nokes	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme
Dr Lynda Isaaka	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme
Livingstone Mumelo	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme
Dr Jimmy Shangala	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme
Dr Teresiah Njoroge	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme
Dennis Kimego	KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme
Dr Osman Warfa	Ministry of Health, Kenya
Dr Celia Muturi	Mama Lucy Kibaki Hospital, Kenya
Dr Elizabeth Jowi	Mama Lucy Kibaki Hospital, Kenya
Dr Lydia Thurania	Kiambu County Referral Hospital, Kenya
Dr Charles Nzioki	Machakos County Referral Hospital, Kenya
Dr Esther Njiru	Embu County Referral Hospital, Kenya
Dr Ngina Mwangi	Embu County Referral Hospital, Kenya
Dr Angeline Ithondeka	Naivasha District Hospital, Kenya
Dr Felicitas Makokha	Bungoma County Referral Hospital, Kenya
Dr Dickens Lubanga	Bungoma County Referral Hospital, Kenya
Dr Emma Namulala	Busia County Referral Hospital, Kenya
Dr Rachel Inginia	Kitale County Referral Hospital, Kenya
Dr Magdaline Kuria	Kisumu East Hospital, Kenya
Dr Achieng Adem	Kisumu East Hospital, Kenya

Dr Maureen Njoroge

Thika Level 5 Hospital, Kenya

Dr Linda Ombito

Nakuru Level 6 Hospital, Kenya

Dr Maureen Muchela

Jaramogi Oginga Odinga Teaching and Referral
Hospital

Dr Roselyn Malangachi

Kakamega County Referral Hospital, Kenya

Dr Peter Aduro

Kakamega County Referral Hospital, Kenya

Ms Emma Beaumont

London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, UK

3. ABSTRACT

Pneumonia is the leading infectious cause of death among children. Inpatient mortality among children with severe pneumonia often exceeds 10%. For more than 30 years, World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines have recommended empirical treatment with a combination of injectable benzylpenicillin or ampicillin plus gentamicin for children at the highest risk of mortality (severe pneumonia). There is growing debate over the appropriateness of the current recommendations for empirical treatment. The first key question this trial seeks to address is whether either injectable amoxicillin-clavulanic acid or ceftriaxone is superior to benzylpenicillin or ampicillin plus gentamicin (standard care) for the treatment of children hospitalised with severe pneumonia.

Some authorities advise against enteral nutrition in severely ill patients, citing concerns of compromised respiratory status and increased risk of aspiration with nasogastric feeding. Evidence to support these concerns is lacking. Further, administration of intravenous fluids demands careful monitoring - a common challenge in many low resource settings. Intravenous fluids are also deficient in nutritive value to match the raised metabolic demands associated with acute illness. The second key question is therefore whether nasogastric feeding is superior to intravenous fluid therapy for supportive management of children with severe pneumonia.

This 3x2 factorial pragmatic randomised controlled trial will aim to recruit 4392 children aged 2-59 months at up to ten hospitals in Kenya, two in Tanzania, and one in Uganda by competitive enrolment. The primary endpoint will be mortality at Day 5 post-enrolment. Secondary outcomes will be length of hospitalisation, time taken to be able to drink, adverse effects related to the antibiotic treatments, and mortality at Day 30.

A more detailed analysis of aetiology and outcomes will be performed on a sub-population of 500 children randomly selected from sites in Kenya representing high and low malaria transmission regions. This sub-study will involve obtaining chest radiographs, collection of nasopharyngeal samples to test for viral pathogens (Respiratory syncytial virus subtypes A and B and Adenovirus), and clinical assessment three months after recruitment.

The study questions being tackled have been identified as research priorities by policy makers at the Ministry of Health in Kenya, WHO and UNICEF. We therefore anticipate the rapid translation of the findings to policy and clinical practice in settings where the burden of pneumonia is highest.

4. INTRODUCTION

4.1. Background Information

Pneumonia is the leading infectious cause of death among young children (1), with inpatient case fatality rates often exceeding 10% for the most severe form of the syndrome (severe pneumonia) (2–4). The case management clinical algorithm currently recommended for use by the World Health Organization (5) (Table 1) was developed to capture the majority of cases of pneumonia that may benefit from antibiotic therapy, under the assumption that severe and fatal presentations were primarily of bacterial origin.

Table 1: World Health Organization 2013 Guidelines for Classification and Management of Childhood Pneumonia

Syndrome	Clinical Signs (in children aged 2 - 59 months with cough and/or difficulty breathing)	Recommended setting for management and antibiotic treatment
Severe pneumonia	Any one of: oxygen saturation < 90%, central cyanosis, severe respiratory distress, inability to drink/breastfeed or vomiting everything, altered consciousness, convulsions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inpatient management • Intravenous benzylpenicillin/ampicillin and gentamicin
Non-severe pneumonia	<p>Lower chest wall indrawing</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Fast breathing (respiratory rate ≥ 50/min if age 2-11 months; ≥ 40/min if age 12-59 months)</p> <p>AND</p> <p>without signs of severe pneumonia</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outpatient management • Oral amoxicillin.

Following the introduction of vaccines against the dominant causes of pneumonia to national immunisation programmes in many low- and middle-income countries, there has been growing debate over the appropriateness of the current recommendations for empirical antibiotic treatment (6,7). Clinicians in sub-Saharan Africa frequently opt for parenteral amoxicillin-clavulanic acid or third-generation cephalosporins over penicillin and gentamicin for empirical first-line therapy of severe pneumonia (3,8) – a practice possibly linked to perceptions of

diminished effectiveness of recommended treatments. Unfortunately, evidence to support (or counter) the use of these alternative regimens is weak.

Pneumonia aetiology

Reliable data on the causes of pneumonia are limited for several reasons: (i) The approaches for definitive microbiological diagnosis (lung aspirates and biopsy) are technically demanding, risky invasive procedures; (ii) The yield from the traditional method of microbiological diagnosis using bacterial blood cultures is low, ranging from 1 – 7% (9,10); (iii) Many patients present to hospital after having received antibiotics, further limiting the yield of diagnostic tests; (iv) There is often difficulty distinguishing harmless commensal organisms from pathogens. Interpretation of results across studies is complicated further by the poor standardisation of case definitions and procedures(11). Unpublished data from a large multi-country case control study of more than 9000 children (including 1200 from a site in coastal Kenya) that were presented in a recent international conference may provide some insight into pneumonia aetiology in the post-pneumococcal vaccine era (12). Consistent with previous studies, only 5% of cases had a positive blood culture. The leading bacterial causes of pneumonia were non-type b *H. influenzae* and *S. pneumoniae* while the most frequently identified virus was Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV).

RSV prevalence in severe ARI (SARI) children under 5 years of age has been estimated from a 4 calendar year surveillance in Kenya to be 21.6% in rural Western Kenya (Lwak, high malaria incidence) and 22.4% in Nairobi (Kibera, no malaria) (13). In a separate study of hospitalised SARI patients under 5 years old in Western Kenya from 4 years of surveillance the prevalence RSV positive as 12% (14); and in Eastern coastal Kenya (Kilifi), from 6 years of surveillance, the prevalence in children under 5 years admitted to hospital with WHO defined severe or very severe pneumonia, was 15% (15). Seasonality patterns differ across Kenya with seasonal peak around February in Eastern parts and around June in the West (13–15). Prevalence estimates may differ due to case ascertainment and definition, detection methods, seasonal and longer-term variation, and (sometimes) geographic location. Optimally, studies should collect data over more than one season, throughout the year, in multiple locations using standard inclusion criteria and screening methods.

In a systematic review of 22 studies on community-acquired bloodstream infections in Africa 3,527 (8.2%) of 43,130 children included had bacteremia (16). Among children with positive blood cultures, gram negative organisms comprised 1926 (54.0%) of isolated organisms (mainly *Salmonella enterica* (21.4%), *Escherichia coli* (9.4%), and *H. influenzae* (8.0%)). The most frequently isolated gram-positive organisms were *S. pneumoniae* (23.3%) and *S. aureus* (12.0%). In this study, bacteremia associated with increased mortality. Of note, however, almost all of the studies included were conducted prior to the introduction of vaccines against *H. influenzae* type B (Hib) and *S. pneumoniae*. The role of gram-negative organisms and *Staphylococcus aureus* among children hospitalised with community-acquired bacteremia in the post-vaccine era remains unclear.

Systemic bacterial infection largely secondary to non-typhoidal salmonella (NTS) is a recognized complication of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria, resulting case fatality as high as 24.1% (95% CI 18.9 to 29.4) (17). The clinical overlap between pneumonia and malaria has been described in various settings (18,19). In the absence of reliable signs to distinguish between the two diseases, the selection of empirical antibiotic regimens for pneumonia in malaria-endemic settings should, therefore, account for the risk of concomitant bacteremia due to NTS and other enteric Gram-negative organisms commonly associated with malaria.

Antimicrobial resistance

Widespread empirical use of penicillin has generated concerns over increasing antimicrobial resistance in the community. However, local data on antibiotic sensitivity are extremely rare. Hospital-based surveillance data from paediatric admissions at a site in coastal Kenya spanning 16 years (1998 – 2014) suggest high susceptibility (>95%) to both penicillin (n=959) and ceftriaxone (n=955) for pneumococcal isolates from children with invasive disease excluding those with meningitis (unpublished microbiology reports, KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme (KWTRP)).

Despite evidence from these limited microbiological data suggesting continued susceptibility in the small number of organisms that could be identified, high rates of mortality continue to be observed even where compliance with guideline-recommended antibiotics is high (20). Most staphylococci are resistant to benzylpenicillin, while gentamicin exhibits poor lung penetration (21). Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, a semisynthetic antibiotic with bactericidal activity covering both gram-negative and gram-positive microorganisms including *S. aureus*, and ceftriaxone, a

third-generation cephalosporin with broad-spectrum gram-negative activity with good tissue penetration, are both widely available alternatives to the standard treatment, are already popular choices among clinicians treating severe pneumonia and they are the recommended first line intravenous (IV) antibiotics for pneumonia in some high-income settings (22). However, there are concerns regarding the widespread use of empirical ceftriaxone linked to the potential for inducing extended spectrum beta lactamase and a resultant increase in resistance across multiple antibiotic groups (23,24). Evidence demonstrating no benefit of ceftriaxone over the standard treatment may serve to strengthen policies promoting antimicrobial stewardship though reinforcing the continued use of the current first line antibiotics.

Previous trials on antibiotic effectiveness for severe childhood pneumonia

In a Cochrane Systematic Review that presents results from two large published studies (n=2074), children with pneumonia presenting with danger signs treated with penicillin plus gentamicin experienced a significantly lower rate of treatment failure compared to those who received chloramphenicol (RR 0.79; 95% CI 0.66 to 0.94) (25). The results of these studies subsequently informed a major revision of the WHO recommendations. However, both studies were conducted prior to the widespread introduction of the *H. influenzae* and pneumococcal conjugate vaccines. The review also discusses a trial that compared penicillin-gentamicin versus amoxicillin-clavulanic acid in 71 children admitted to a tertiary hospital in India (26). This study reported no difference between the two treatments, possibly due to the small sample size. Another small trial compared penicillin versus ceftriaxone in 97 children aged 2 - 24 months in Turkey and also demonstrated no difference in clinical outcomes (27). The authors of the review acknowledge the low methodological quality of these two studies and recommend more studies to examine the effectiveness of these alternative regimens. The review also discusses the need for research on interventions besides antibiotics, such as those targeting supportive care. There are currently no published clinical trials comparing benzylpenicillin or ampicillin plus gentamicin versus ceftriaxone.

Previous trials comparing nasogastric feeding versus intravenous fluids for severe childhood pneumonia

Inadequate supportive care may provide an alternative explanation for the high case fatality for severe pneumonia. In low-income settings with limited capacity to deliver advanced critical care, there is lack of consensus regarding the appropriate practice for providing nutritional and fluid management to children with signs of severe respiratory illness. A landmark trial on fluid

resuscitation for African children with severe infection and impaired circulation exposed the poor evidence base for supportive care and possible risks associated with intravenous fluid management (28). Guidelines recommending the avoidance of enteral feeding for children cite risks of aspiration and compromised respiratory function with nasogastric feeding based on weak evidence from a small number of preterm infants weighing below 2000g (22,29). An additional theoretical basis to withhold enteral feeding in patients with hypoxaemia is to limit oxygen consumption and carbon dioxide production. However, the process of starving mobilises endogenous stores and is energy-consuming (30). Factors that may reduce the efficacy of enteral nutrition and favour the intravenous route in critically ill patients include gastrointestinal hypoperfusion and use of opioid-containing analgesics that may delay gastrointestinal transit time. Studies in animals have shown that large fluid resuscitation volumes may result in a generalized intestinal edema, significantly impairing gut function (31).

Nasogastric feeding is however potentially advantageous because of the supply of additional nutrition to support the increased metabolic requirements experienced during episodes of severe acute illness. Evidence comparing enteral nutrition versus intravenous fluids for providing supportive care in critically ill children are extremely limited. A recent clinical trial comparing the two routes of treatment for 381 infants with bronchiolitis in New Zealand reported similar outcomes for the two approaches and the advantage of higher success rates of insertion for the nasogastric route (32). Despite a lack of direct evidence, the 2017 European Society of Intensive Care Medicine (ESICM) guideline recommends early enteral feeding within 48 hours for adult patients with stable hypoxaemia (33). The guideline further states that early enteral nutrition may help to preserve gut mucosal integrity and the microbiome.

Relevant planned, ongoing or recently completed trials internationally

A recent trial in Malawi compared ceftriaxone versus penicillin and gentamicin in severe neonatal sepsis and bacterial meningitis (n=348) and found no difference in deaths or sequela including hearing loss between the treatment groups. This study only included infants aged <2months with different diagnoses (34).

A recently concluded trial in Bangladesh compared inpatient versus day care of stable children aged 2 – 59 months with pneumonia and malnutrition using injectable ceftriaxone (n = 440) (NCT00968370). The findings of this study may contribute complementary data to our trial.

An ongoing clinical trial in Kenya compared ceftriaxone versus benzylpenicillin plus

gentamicin and metronidazole versus placebo for children with complicated severe acute malnutrition (NCT02746276). The data from children with severe pneumonia recruited in this trial may contribute complementary evidence to the proposed trial.

4.2. Justification

Currently available methods for determining the pathogens causing severe pneumonia in children admitted for routine hospital care in much of sub-Saharan Africa are unreliable. Understanding actual treatment effects by conducting high quality pragmatic clinical trials for treatments targeting potentially important causes of pneumonia in the post-pneumococcal/Hib vaccine era (specifically gram-negative organisms and *S. aureus*) therefore becomes ever more important. Emerging research on the risks of intravenous fluid management for sick children and poor evidence for existing practices suggest a need for clinical trials testing alternative approaches to delivering supportive fluids/feeds in settings that lack resources to provide advanced critical care. Evidence demonstrating no benefit of ceftriaxone over the standard treatment may serve to strengthen policies promoting antimicrobial stewardship though reinforcing the continued use of the current first line antibiotics.

The ability to provide policy makers with data on outcomes of treatment in typical settings where children often have co-morbid conditions as well as information on the comparative effectiveness of treatments is a critical consideration for this highly pragmatic clinical trial. This is particularly pertinent for pneumonia given the prior rejection of suggested policy changes despite evidence from previous clinical trials related to concerns of the lack of generalizability of the available evidence (35). This approach will also strengthen routine systems in the hospitals while engaging those working within these systems much more closely in the research process and ultimately promoting knowledge translation.

Aetiology sub-study

To explore possible heterogeneity in treatment effects and provide useful information to classify patients according to likely pathology (pneumonia versus other causes of respiratory distress), chest radiographs and nasopharyngeal samples (to test for RSV and Adenovirus) will be collected in a sub-population of children enrolled in this trial. There is emerging evidence that among children who survive the severe acute respiratory illness and are discharged home, there is continuing risk of persisting morbidity, particularly among those with viral pneumonia

(36). There is limited understanding of the magnitude, severity, spectrum and risk factors for continued morbidity and/or mortality in these children in an African setting. Research that gives insight into this problem will be useful for early identification of at-risk children, and guide planning & development of specific mid-term and long-term chronic care protocols and services that would improve disease free survival, minimise development of sequelae, and optimise long-term care for those with chronic disease sequelae.

5. TRIAL OBJECTIVES AND PURPOSE

5.1. Null hypotheses

- (i) Mortality amongst children admitted to hospital with severe pneumonia is not altered by administration of either intravenous amoxicillin/clavulanic acid or ceftriaxone as first-line treatments compared to the standard WHO-recommended treatment (benzyl penicillin or ampicillin and gentamicin).
- (ii) Mortality amongst children admitted to hospital with severe pneumonia is not altered by administration of enteral nutrition via the nasogastric route as immediate supportive therapy compared to intravenous maintenance fluids.

5.2. Primary objectives

Among children with severe pneumonia, this study aims to determine whether:

- (i) Mortality is reduced within five days when treated with either ceftriaxone or intravenous amoxicillin/clavulanic acid, compared to currently recommended benzyl penicillin or ampicillin and gentamicin.
- (ii) Mortality is reduced within five days when enteral nutrition is administered via the nasogastric route as immediate supportive therapy, compared to intravenous maintenance fluids.

5.3. Secondary objective(s)

To assess in both interventions:

- (i) Safety as defined by any serious adverse events likely or definitely related to intervention.
- (ii) Length of hospital stay
- (iii) Duration taken to tolerate full fluid requirements by mouth
- (iv) Mortality 30 days after enrolment

5.3.1. Aetiology sub-study

A more detailed assessment of aetiology and outcomes will be performed on a sub-population of children randomly-selected from sites in Kenya representing high and low malaria transmission regions. This sub-study will involve obtaining chest radiographs and collection of nasopharyngeal swab samples to test for Respiratory syncytial virus (the most commonly isolated pathogen in large multi-country case control study on pneumonia aetiology (12)), and Adenovirus as soon as possible after recruitment, and clinical assessments three months after recruitment. These additional data will provide useful information to classify patients according to likely pathology (pneumonia versus other causes of respiratory distress). Bacterial blood cultures will not be performed in this study due to the low yield of this method for microbiological diagnosis of pneumonia (1 – 7%) (9,10)

6. TRIAL DESIGN

6.1. Overall Study Design and Plan Description

We propose a multi-centre open label, pragmatic 3x2 factorial individually-randomised controlled superiority trial. The factorial design will optimise efficiency by allowing for the testing of two questions that have been identified as research priorities by policy makers at the Ministry of Health in Kenya, WHO and UNICEF. Two randomisations will be made (see Figure 1). The two interventions (antibiotics and supportive care) will be analysed separately.

NG – nasogastric

IV - Intravenous

Figure 1: Factorial randomisation scheme

Study participants will undergo a series of processes summarized in Table 2. All eligible participants will be allocated to the assigned study interventions on the day of enrolment. A chest radiograph and a nasopharyngeal swab will be taken from a sub-population of children randomly-selected from sites in Kenya representing high and low malaria transmission regions. Registration of the study endpoints will take place throughout the inpatient stay, and by caregiver telephone interview at 30 days after enrolment. The children sampled to participate in the aetiology sub-study will undergo a clinical review to determine the presence of residual morbidity 90 days after enrolment.

Table 2: Summary of study processes

Timepoint	0h	24h	48h	72h	96h	5 d	30 d	90 d
Enrolment								
Screening	●—●							
Informed consent	●—→							
Randomization	●—●							
Study procedures								
Antibiotic treatment	●—→							
NG feeds/IV fluids	●—→							
Chest radiograph*	●—●							
Nasopharyngeal swab*	●—●							
Assessments								
Primary endpoint	●—●							
Secondary endpoints	●—●							
Assessment for persisting morbidity*							●—●	

* Aetiology sub-study only

7. SELECTION OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS

7.1. Description of the population to be studied

7.1.1. Study sites

The study will be conducted at up to 15 public hospitals in East Africa (Table 3). The proposed sites include ten hospitals in Kenya, one in Mwanza in north western Tanzania, and one in Jinja, in southern Uganda. Including sites in three countries is expected to enhance the generalisability of the results and to ultimately increase the potential impact of the study on policy and practice in the region.

The investigators have been working in collaboration with the Ministry of Health in seven of the nine Kenyan hospitals implementing a system for collecting routine inpatient data and using the data to improve quality of care through a process of audit and feedback. The study settings are typical of “district-level” hospitals in the region, where diagnostic capacity is often limited and facilities to provide advanced critical care for severely ill children are unavailable. All 12 facilities offer both primary care and referral services.

Table 3: Proposed study sites and locations

Hospital	Location
Mama Lucy Kibaki Hospital	Central Kenya, low malaria transmission
Kiambu County Referral Hospital	Central Kenya, low malaria transmission
Machakos County Referral Hospital	Central Kenya, low malaria transmission
Embu County Referral Hospital	Central Kenya, low malaria transmission
Naivasha County Hospital	Central Kenya, low malaria transmission
Thika Level 5 Hospital	Central Kenya, low malaria transmission
Nakuru Level 6 Hospital	Central Kenya, low malaria transmission
Bungoma County Referral Hospital	Western Kenya, high malaria transmission
Busia County Referral Hospital	Western Kenya, high malaria transmission
Kakamega County Referral Hospital	Western Kenya, high malaria transmission
Kitale County Referral Hospital	Western Kenya, high malaria transmission
Kisumu East Hospital	Western Kenya, high malaria transmission
Jaramogi Oginga Odinga Teaching and Referral Hospital	Western Kenya, high malaria transmission
Migori County Referral Hospital	Western Kenya, high malaria transmission
Bugando Medical Centre	North Western Tanzania, high malaria transmission
Jinja Regional Referral Hospital	Southern Uganda, high malaria transmission

7.1.2. Screening

Patient screening and enrolment will take place in the paediatric emergency units or paediatric wards of participating hospitals depending on the system in place at each hospital. The

screening process will be based on the standard WHO criteria for severe pneumonia which are in use at all study hospitals. A screening log will document all potentially eligible children. All children presenting with a wheeze will receive a full course of inhaled bronchodilator therapy prior to screening for eligibility.

7.1.3. Inclusion criteria

- Age 2 to 59 months.
- History of cough or difficulty breathing and signs of severe pneumonia based on WHO 2013 criteria (5) (Table 1).
- Admitted to any one of the study hospitals.
- Informed consent provided by the parents/guardian.

7.1.4. Exclusion criteria

- Children presenting in cardiorespiratory arrest requiring emergency basic life support (bag-valve-mask ventilation and/or chest compressions).
- Children for whom concurrent condition precludes the use of the first-line antibiotics for severe pneumonia such as readmission or meningitis
- Shock due to dehydration or severe dehydration (based on WHO definitions (5)) requiring emergency fluid resuscitation
- Known allergy or contraindication to penicillin, gentamicin, ceftriaxone or amoxicillin-clavulanic acid.
- Referral from another inpatient facility following treatment with injectable antibiotics for more than 24 hours or because the first-line regimen is considered to have failed
- Previously enrolled in the study.
- For Randomisation 2 (IV fluid versus nasogastric feeds): children with absent gag reflex.
- For Randomisation 2 (IV fluid versus nasogastric feeds): children unable to maintain oxygen saturations $\geq 90\%$ on pulse oximetry while receiving supplemental oxygen.
- For Randomisation 2 (IV fluid versus nasogastric feeds): children with severe acute malnutrition

7.2. Enrolment

Recruitment will be through competitive enrolment with a minimum of 200 and a maximum of 800 patients per site. Enrolment will occur at the time of admission. Parental or guardianship status of the accompanying adult will be verified verbally by the admitting clinician for all potential study participants. Details of the study will then be communicated to the parent(s)/guardian(s). Deferred written informed consent will be sought from caregivers accompanying study patients to prevent delays in the administration of emergency care including administration of IV antimicrobials (37). This process, commonly implemented in clinical trials taking place in emergency situations (38–41), entails a short verbal assent process from caregivers at the time of enrolment by a trained study clinician or nurse followed later by full written consent after stabilising the child (within 24 hours of recruitment). The information given during this verbal assent process includes key elements of the International Conference on Harmonisation Good Clinical Practice (ICH-GCP) recommendations. For children who die prior to the obtaining full written consent, assent will be used as permission to be included the trial and use of their data.

8. WITHDRAWAL OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Subjects may be withdrawn from the study:

- By withdrawing consent (data for patients whose caregivers withdraw consent for use of their child's data will be deleted from the study database).
- On the decision of the investigator (including the site Principal Investigator who is the paediatrician at each site)

The investigator may withdraw the subject for the following reasons:

- Any adverse event which results in the inability to comply with study procedures
- Any medical need necessitating a change in treatment determined by the paediatrician in-charge or designee
- Ineligibility either arising during the study or retrospectively
- Significant protocol deviation.

The reason for withdrawal will be recorded in the CRF.

9. TREATMENT OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Patients will be assigned to study treatments in a two-stage randomization process (Figure 1):

Randomisation 1:

- IV benzyl penicillin or ampicillin plus gentamicin (standard care)
- IV ceftriaxone
- IV amoxicillin-clavulanic acid

Randomisation 2:

- Intravenous maintenance fluids (widely preferred standard care)
- Nasogastric feeds (may include any of the following commonly available preparations appropriate to the child's age: expressed breastmilk, commercial milk formula, pasteurized cow's milk, porridge or other blended foods as per caregiver/ hospital practice)

9.1. Investigational Products

9.2. Name and description of the investigational product(s)

Trial lots of all investigational products will be procured directly from the manufacturer through locally-approved channels for each country with accompanying batch release certificates. Quality control will be maintained by a WHO accredited lab in Nairobi (National Quality Control Laboratories) which will collect and analyse random samples of study drugs to confirm sufficient and consistent levels of active ingredient.

Benzyl penicillin / ampicillin

Quality-assured benzyl penicillin / ampicillin will be supplied to the study sites and used at standard recommended doses. Benzyl penicillin and ampicillin are licensed for use in children in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania.

Gentamicin

Quality-assured gentamicin will be supplied to the study sites and used at standard recommended doses. Gentamicin is licensed for use in children in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania.

Ceftriaxone

Quality-assured ceftriaxone will be supplied to the study sites and used at standard recommended doses. Ceftriaxone is licensed for use in children in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania.

Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid

Quality-assured amoxicillin-clavulanic will be supplied to the study sites and used at standard recommended doses. Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid is licensed for use in children in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania.

9.2.1. Storage

Study drugs will be stored at the sites as per manufacturers' recommendations.

9.2.2. Dosing

Intervention 1:

- Benzyl penicillin 50 000 IU/kg every 6 hours or ampicillin 50mg/kg every 8 hours IM or IV for at least 48 hours and up to 7 days plus gentamicin 7.5 mg/kg IM or IV once a day for up to 7 days (given inpatient).
or
- Ceftriaxone 50 mg/kg IM or IV every 12 hours for up to 7 days (given inpatient).
or
- Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid 30mg/kg IM or IV every 8 hours for up to 7 days (given inpatient)

In all three antibiotic treatment groups, injectable antibiotics will be given for a minimum of 48 hours, with the option of early discharge in cases of rapid recovery on oral amoxicillin (40 - 45 mg/kg) every 12 hours to complete minimum 5 days of treatment with duration determined by the paediatrician leading care locally.

First-line antimicrobial treatment for children with specific and documented clinical, radiological or laboratory indications for second-line antibiotics may be changed under guidance from the site clinical lead or individual designated the role, or other investigators in line with local treatment protocols aimed at ensuring optimum care. Details of any changes in treatment will be recorded in the CRF, along with the reason.

Intervention 2:

- Ringers Lactate solution with 5% dextrose or normal (0.9%) saline solution with 5% dextrose administered as a continuous infusion for at least 24 hours, until the child is able to take adequate oral fluids by mouth without the need for supplemental IV fluids.
or
- Nasogastric feeds administered as a slow bolus over at least 20 minutes every 3 hours for at least 24 hours, until the child is able to take adequate oral fluids by mouth without the need for supplemental nasogastric feeds/fluids

Both supportive care interventions will be administered at standard daily maintenance volumes based on admission weight (100ml/kg for the first 10 kg; 50ml/kg for each additional kg up to 20kg; and 20ml/kg for each additional kg).

9.2.3. Dispensing Procedures

Each site will designate a pharmacist or other suitably qualified and trained employees (designees) to dispense trial drugs.

9.2.4. Dose Administration

Dose administration will be by trained hospital nurses with additional training to all ward staff. Precautions to minimize the risk for aspiration and limit work of breathing will include nursing in the propped-up position, minimal handling, confirmation of nasogastric tube placement, and assessment for residual gastric contents before administration of nasogastric feeds as part of standard practice.

9.2.5. Accountability

The trial coordinator will maintain accurate records with sufficient information to provide a full audit trail from the receipt of the study products to their removal from site or destruction.

9.2.6. Treatment Compliance

All treatments administered to study participants will be recorded daily in the study CRF. Missed doses will also be logged.

9.3. Randomisation and Allocation Concealment

The random allocation sequence will be computer-generated at the KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme according to a block randomisation list of random block sizes for each site. At each site, a study computer will be programmed with the random allocation sequence (separately assigned for each of the two randomizations shown in Figure 1). This will be done in a secure manner to avoid any possibility of viewing the allocation sequence. The study clinical officer at each site will enter the patient's details into the computer and only then the allocation will be revealed. The site will revert to random allocation using the next numbered sealed opaque envelope as the back-up option if the computer-based randomization fails.

Randomisation codes linking allocation to study number will be held by the statistician until the database is unlocked. The local monitor and chair of the DSMB can request for randomisation codes from the statistician in case of an individual safety concern. Due to the nature of the study treatments (varying dosing schedules for antibiotics and IV versus enterally administered supportive treatments), blinding for the assessment of outcome will not be practical. This limitation is however mitigated by the objective nature of mortality as a primary outcome.

9.4. Clinical care

Children will be managed to the best standard available in each study hospital, in line with national and WHO recommendations. We will aim to deliver the study interventions under conditions representative of typical settings in Kenyan, Ugandan and Tanzanian public hospitals. Thus, we will employ a fulltime experienced clinical officer at each site to take responsibility for participant recruitment and inpatient follow up of study patients. Clinical officers are licensed medical professionals with authority to provide paediatric care equivalent to that of medical officers. Study clinical officers will work under direct supervision of their respective hospital paediatricians.

Intravenous cannulae and nasogastric tubes will be inserted by hospital nurses trained on the study SOPs for administration of intravenous treatments and nasogastric tube insertion (including testing for gag reflex). Injectable treatments including intravenous fluids will be administered by hospital nurses. Nurses will initiate nasogastric feeding and ensure competence of mothers to continue once safety is established (as per current practice).

Decisions on clinical and nursing management will be made at the discretion of ward-based hospital staff with access to routinely available resources only, and with care supervised by the hospital paediatrician, who are assigned the role of site Principal Investigator. Adequate quantities of the study treatments will be supplied to the study sites for patient care. Additional care such as oxygen therapy will be provided in line with recommended practice under the guidance of the on-site paediatricians at the study hospitals. Hospital will be supported to perform routine testing for haemoglobin levels, microscopy for malaria, and HIV rapid tests for study participants in line with recommended guidance. Other routine admission blood tests may include a full blood count, glucose, biochemistry and blood culture (based on availability).

9.5. Collection of data, samples and chest radiography

Data on socio-demographic and clinical attributes of the enrolled children will be recorded through direct interview of their caregivers on paper-based CRFs adapted from standard structured hospital admission forms. Details on comorbidities, results for investigations requested (including haemoglobin levels, routine HIV testing and malaria parasitological diagnosis), and all treatments prescribed and administered will be documented.

Chest radiography

Chest radiographs will be obtained for a random sample of enrolled participants as soon as feasible after admission but within the first 48 hours. Films will be interpreted onsite by the paediatrician to aid in clinical care. Each film will also be viewed by a second study paediatrician and reported using the WHO standardized methodology for the interpretation of pediatric chest radiographs (42) with a third arbitrator to review discordant reports.

Nasopharyngeal samples

Nasopharyngeal (NP) swabs will be collected in the same sample of children on whom chest radiographs will be performed. On collection, swabs will be put into a 1ml vial of viral transport medium, the vial placed in a cool box with icepacks and transported to the local laboratory and stored at -80°C freezer or -20°C as available (15). Samples will periodically be transferred from the holding lab to KWTRP on dry ice for processing, investigation and storage (at -80°C). Ribonucleic acid (RNA) will be extracted from NP swabs using commercially available kits. RNA extract will be screened for RSV using a real time PCR assay specific to groups A and B (43,44). Samples with cycle threshold values of <35.0 will be deemed positive. RSV positives will be subject to further analysis to detect genotypes and variants that may relate to transmission or pathogenicity (45), using Sanger or Next Generation Sequencing methods, such as, but not limited to, the methods set up in the KWTRP lab (46,47). Residual NP and RNA sample will be stored for future studies relating to the microbial aetiology of severe pneumonia. There will be no further samples taken and stored from study participants for research.

9.6. Follow up

9.6.1. During admission

Daily follow-up data on inpatient clinical progress (including clinical deterioration, SAE or suspected toxicity) and clinical outcome will continue until hospital discharge or death.

9.6.2. Follow up after hospital discharge

Caregivers will be requested to provide up to two mobile phone contacts which will be used to facilitate follow-up and capture information on any deaths, morbidity and readmissions within 30 days of enrolment through a telephone interview. Study clinicians will be trained on conducting telephone interviews sensitively. Telephone follow-up has been successfully implemented in a previous clinical trial with a follow up rate of 94% (48). Caregivers who cannot be contacted by telephone will be provided an appointment at the hospital for a clinical review 30 days after enrolment, while those selected to participate in the aetiology sub-study will be provided clinical appointment at the hospital 90 days after enrolment. Reimbursement for out-of-pocket costs associated with taking part will be provided at each scheduled visit, in line with KEMRI Centre for Geographic Medicine Research - Coast (CGMR-C) Guidelines for Study Benefits and Out-of-Pocket Expenses. Data on clinical status for this outcome will be collected through verbal clinical inquiry to determine if alive, fully recovered, or the presence of persisting morbidity. Children identified to have persisting morbidity on telephone clinical assessment shall be encouraged to return for follow-up clinical review and management at the hospital as per standard of care. Study clinicians will be trained on obtaining verbal consent from caregivers and conducting interviews for verbal autopsy sensitively.

10. ASSESSMENT OF SAFETY

10.1. Toxicity, Serious Adverse Events and Unexpected Events

Safety oversight will be the responsibility of the investigators led by the PI, and the Data Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB).

10.1.1. Suspected Toxicity

Ceftriaxone and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid are licensed drugs with known safety profiles. Assessment of safety will therefore focus on severe and causally related events. Clinical or laboratory toxicity will be reported if they are grade 4 according to the Division of AIDS (DAIDS) Table for Grading the Severity of Adverse Events (Table 4) (49).

Table 4: Pre-defined Grade 4 suspected toxicity events

Allergic and Cutaneous reactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Anaphylaxis• Bronchospasm requiring treatment
---	--

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exfoliative dermatitis 												
Severe anaemia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Severe anaemia Hb <4g/dl 												
Neutropenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Neutrophil count <0.4 x 10⁹ /L 												
Thrombocytopenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platelets <25 x 10⁹ /L 												
Encephalopathy & Neurological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impaired consciousness –AVPU: P or U Convulsions New focal neurological signs 												
Abnormal renal function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creatinine >3.5 x upper limit of normal (>138 µmol/L) 												
Abnormal liver function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One or more of: Transaminases or gamma-glutamyl transferase >10 x upper limit of normal: <table style="margin-left: 40px;"> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">ALT</td> <td style="text-align: right;">>450</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">IU/L</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">AST</td> <td style="text-align: right;">>620</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">IU/L</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">ALP</td> <td style="text-align: right;">>4,060</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: right;">IU/L</td> <td></td> </tr> </table> Bilirubin >5 x upper limit of normal >63 µmol/L 	ALT	>450	IU/L		AST	>620	IU/L		ALP	>4,060	IU/L	
ALT	>450												
IU/L													
AST	>620												
IU/L													
ALP	>4,060												
IU/L													

Adapted from Division of AIDS (DAIDS) Table for Grading the Severity of Adverse Events (49)

10.1.2. Serious Adverse Events (SAE)

An adverse event (whether or not considered related to the investigational product) resulting in any of the following outcomes is defined as an SAE:

- Death (from any cause at any time)
- Life-threatening event (i.e., the subject was, in the view of the investigator, at immediate risk of death from the event that occurred).
- Persistent or significant disability or incapacity (i.e., substantial disruption of ability to carry out normal life functions).
- Hospitalisation or an important medical event requiring medical or surgical intervention to prevent one of the outcomes listed above. Examples include severe adverse drug

reactions such as severe allergic reaction or blood dyscrasias requiring intensive treatment.

10.1.3. Suspected and Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction (SUSAR)

These are the reactions that are serious (as defined above) but not expected AND considered to be related to the investigational product. This definition captures the important events that are attributed to the product but do not follow known pattern of response to study product.

10.1.4. Adverse Events Assessment of Causality

An assessment of the relationship of the event to the study drug will be undertaken by the senior clinical investigators who will remain blinded to study allocation. This interpretation will be based on the type of event, the relationship of the event to the time of administration, and the known biology of the intervention (Table 5). The following are guidelines for assessing the relationship of administration of the product to the AE.

Table 5: Guidelines for assessing the relationship of drug administration to an Adverse event

0	No Relationship	No temporal relationship to drug and alternate aetiology (clinical state, environmental or other interventions); and does not follow known pattern of response to study product
1	Unlikely	Unlikely temporal relationship to drug and alternate aetiology likely (clinical state, environmental or other interventions) and does not follow known typical or plausible pattern of response to drug.
2	Possible	Reasonable temporal relationship to drug; or event not readily produced by clinical state, environmental or other interventions; or similar pattern of response to that seen with other drugs
3	Probable	Reasonable temporal relationship to drug; and event not readily produced by clinical state, environment, or other interventions or known pattern of response seen with other drugs
4	Definite	Reasonable temporal relationship to drug; and event not readily produced by clinical state, environment, or other interventions; and known pattern of response seen with other drugs

10.1.5. Emergency Procedures

In the event of an abnormal clinical or laboratory finding by the study clinician, children will receive appropriate treatment according to national or WHO clinical guidelines, including admission for assessment and/or treatment where appropriate. Usual clinical practice for suspected reactions to study drugs will be followed.

10.1.6. Follow up of adverse events

Serious Adverse Events will be followed up by the investigator until their resolution or stabilisation or until causality is determined to be unrelated to trial interventions. The outcome will be assessed as:

- Recovered/resolved
- Not recovered/not resolved
- Recovering/resolving
- Recovered with sequelae/resolved with sequelae
- Fatal

10.1.7. Assessment of Causes of Death

An endpoint review committee, comprising two individuals experienced in paediatric care in sub-Saharan Africa, will review all clinical, laboratory and radiological information for children who die during the trial to determine the causes of death that will be used in the final analysis. The endpoint review committee will remain blinded to the randomised allocations.

10.2. Reporting of Toxicity, SAEs & SUSARS

Because the study population is known to have a high rate of mortality (approximately 14%) (4), deterioration and readmission, a high background rate of SAEs is expected. SAEs that are deemed probably and definitely causally related to the study drug and SUSARs will be initially reported to the local study monitor, DSMB, and the ethical review committees (SERU, PPB-ECCT and OXTREC) within 48 hours of the investigators becoming aware of the event with a follow up report being provided within a further five working days. A summary of all other SAEs and suspected toxicity events will be reported every 3 months. The report will include the site; study number; date of event; subject details (initials, sex and age); nature of event; relevant history; outcome and a judgement of causality.

11. PROTOCOL DEVIATIONS

The investigators will conduct the trial in compliance with the protocol agreed to by the sponsor and which was given approval by the ethical review committees and regulatory authority. The PI will sign the protocol to confirm agreement. The investigators will not implement any deviation from, or changes of the protocol without agreement by the sponsor and prior review and documented approval from SERU, PPB, and OxtREC of an amendment, except where necessary to eliminate an immediate hazard(s) to trial subjects, or when the change(s) involve only logistical or administrative aspects of the trial (e.g., change in monitor(s), change of telephone number(s)). The investigator, or person designated by the PI, will document and explain any deviation from the approved protocol in the protocol deviation file. The investigator may implement a deviation from, or a change of, the protocol to eliminate an immediate hazard(s) to trial subjects without prior ethics approval. As soon as possible, the implemented deviation or change, the reasons for it, and, if appropriate, the proposed protocol amendment(s) should be submitted: to ethics for review and approval and to the sponsor for agreement if required. A protocol deviations folder will contain documentation of all deviations from the protocol and their justification.

12. QUALITY CONTROL AND QUALITY ASSURANCE

The PI will ensure that staff involved with the trial are:

- Properly qualified to assume responsibility for conduct of the study
- Willing to comply with GCP and applicable regulations
- Prepared for audits and monitoring
- Able to recruit study participants in sufficient numbers and on time
- Well informed about the protocol, the Investigational Products, and their study responsibilities

The site clinical leads will ensure that their respective sites have:

- Sufficient human and material resources to sustain routine standards of care
- Staff who are well informed about the protocol, the IP, and their study responsibilities and are fully trained in the relevant SOPs

The study will be monitored by the KEMRI/Wellcome Clinical Trials Facility Monitoring Team, who will develop a risk-based monitoring plan for the study. The monitoring team comprises of trial coordinators and trial managers from the various trials currently running

within the unit. To achieve independence during the monitoring, one dedicated study monitor, independent of the study team, will be assigned to monitor this study.

The monitor's role is part of the quality system and will oversee the progress of the trial and ensure that the trial is conducted and data are handled in accordance with trial SOPs, the protocol, Good Clinical Practice (GCP) and applicable ethical and regulatory requirements.

13. DATA MANAGEMENT

13.1. Data collection

13.1.1. Participant data

The study will generate quantitative data from inpatient clinical reviews captured on a paper CRF and single-entered daily into a GCP-compliant web-based database (Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) (50)), either as an update of an existing record or as a new record for new study patients at the study hospitals and telephone interviews or outpatient clinical assessments (late outcomes), supplementary quality checks will also be performed and these will be detailed in the Data Management Plan. Clinical data will include sociodemographic characteristics, findings on clinical assessment, treatments administered during the period of hospitalisation and clinical outcome following treatment, captured from one daily review for approximately 5 days and one follow up review 30 days after recruitment.

13.2. Data storage

De-identified data will be entered remotely at the sites and synched daily to central secure password-restricted institutional servers hosted at the KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme, with regular secure backup over a secure 3G or fiberoptic internet connection. These are secure high capacity servers with automated daily mirror back-up to prevent catastrophic loss of data. The data will be retained by the KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme. The database will generate automated queries and the investigators or monitors may generate manual queries related to clinical care and data management. All queries will be dealt with by the site clinicians and clarified by the site study leads and other site staff with clear documentation. We will utilize the inbuilt access management and audit trail functions of REDCap to implement role assignment and restrict unauthorized access to study data. No names will appear on stored documents, scanned forms or transcripts.

The investigators will permit trial-related monitoring, audits, reviews by the ethical review committees, and regulatory inspections by providing direct access to CRFs, source data and other trial-related documents. The PI will be responsible for receiving, entering, cleaning, querying, analysing and storing all data that accrues from the study. Responsibility for this may be delegated to the study data management team.

14. STATISTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

14.1. Determination of sample size

We estimate cumulative mortality at Day 5 in the reference groups (penicillin / gentamicin or intravenous fluids) to be approximately 12%, based on data from local studies (2,3) including an observational study of >3000 children with severe pneumonia hospitalised at the proposed study hospitals (4).

We aim to enrol 4392 participants. With this sample size, the study will have 90% power to detect a 30% relative reduction in mortality (4% absolute reduction) across the antibiotic intervention groups with a two-tailed alpha fixed at 2.5% to allow for multiple comparisons with an inflation of 5% for patients who may drop out of the study. This calculation is based on the clinical assumption of no interaction between the two interventions (antibiotics and nasogastric feeds/intravenous fluid therapy). The same sample size will allow for the detection of a relative reduction in mortality as low as 25% (3% absolute reduction) in the nasogastric feeds against the intravenous fluid therapy treatment arm (assuming baseline mortality of 12%, two-tailed alpha also set at 2.5%, and after exclusions are applied). A previous clinical trial that recruited children with pneumonia at some of the proposed study sites reported inpatient loss to follow up of <1% (48). Given the severe presentation of the target study population, we expect minimal drop-outs. The primary analyses will be by intention-to-treat.

14.1.1. Sample size for aetiology sub-study

A more detailed assessment of aetiology and outcomes will be performed on a sub-population of 500 children randomly-selected from sites in Kenya representing high and low malaria transmission regions. This sub-study will involve obtaining chest radiographs and collection of nasopharyngeal samples to test for viral pathogens (RSV and adenovirus) and a scheduled clinical assessment three months after recruitment. Below we provide the expected bounds of precision for prevalence of each of the sub-study outcomes to be reported with 95% confidence

intervals (CI) (51).

The proposed sample size will allow for the estimation of prevalence of RSV or Adenovirus within a margin of $\pm 3.6\%$ assuming a prevalence of 22% in both high and low malaria transmission regions (13).

We will estimate the of prevalence of pathological findings on chest radiographs within a margin of $\pm 4.7\%$, assuming 15% of chest radiographs taken will be uninterpretable and 54% will reflect pathology (consolidation and/or other infiltrate) (52)).

The risk of persisting morbidity among children alive 90 days after enrolment will be estimated within a margin of $\pm 3.6\%$ assuming prevalence of long-term sequelae among children hospitalized with pneumonia of 13.6% (36), mortality of 14% (4) and loss to follow up among survivors of up to 20%.

Sampling of patients to be enrolled in the aetiology sub-study will be stratified over a 12-month duration at each participating site to account for seasonal variation of circulating respiratory viruses.

14.2. Planned statistical methods

Analysis of the two interventions will be conducted by the trial statistician separately, as if two separate trials. The primary analyses will be by intention-to-treat. Analysis will follow a pre-specified analysis plan approved by the TSC and DSMB prior to unblinding the study database. The criterion for statistical significance at the final analysis will be $P < 0.05$. Screening, enrolment, reasons for non-enrolment, randomisation and loss to follow up will be detailed in a CONSORT diagram. The rate of loss to follow up will be reported. Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics will be summarized for each randomised group. We will report risk ratios for mortality five days after enrolment (primary outcome) and 30 days after enrolment (secondary outcome) for intervention versus control treatments with associated 95% confidence intervals. The assumption of no interaction between the study antibiotic and supportive care treatments will be studied in exploratory analyses. Other secondary outcomes: length of hospital stay and duration taken to tolerate oral feeds, will be analysed using Kaplan-Meier plots and the hazard ratios with accompanying 95% CI calculated using Cox proportional hazards regression. Suspected toxicity events and SAEs during administration of investigational products will be described along with the proportion of participants affected and compared between randomised groups as risk ratios. The primary analyses for all outcomes will

be by intention to treat. We will also report results of per protocol analyses and complier average causal effects to account for children for whom major protocol violations were recorded such as those relating to non-compliance with the study treatments.

Pre-specified subgroup analyses will be conducted by HIV status and the following clinical characteristics that emerged as independent risk factors for mortality in an analysis of >16,000 children with pneumonia hospitalised at the proposed study sites (4): nutritional status, age (infants versus older children), presence or absence of malaria and presence or absence of pallor.

We will conduct the primary analysis upon conclusion of patient recruitment. One scheduled interim analysis will be performed by an independent statistician once approximately half of the total sample size is achieved. Unblinded data for the main study outcomes and SAEs will be presented to the Data and Safety Monitoring Board (DSMB) by the statistician for review. Results will not be shared with investigators unless DSMB determines a need to do so. Using the Haybittle-Peto adjustment for multiple testing, the DSMB may recommend to the TSC that recruitment be halted if the p-value from a test of difference between any two study groups is determined to be ≤ 0.001 .

15. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

Any intellectual property rights that arise from the work will be safeguarded according to the current KEMRI guidelines and the Industrial Property Act of 2001, sections 32, 58 and 80. The scientific and intellectual contributions of all persons involved in the research will be appropriately acknowledged in all publications and presentations arising from the work.

16. TIME FRAME FOR THE TRIAL

	2018		2019				2020				2021				2022	
	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2
Scientific & ethical approval																
Investigational Product testing																
Procurement of supplies																
Database set up																
Project set-up																
Training																
Trial initiation																
Recruitment & follow up																
Trial close out																
Analysis																
Public engagement																
Reporting & Dissemination																

17. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The proposal will be subject to ethical approval from the KEMRI Scientific and Ethical Review Unit, Kenya Pharmacy and Poisons Board, the respective nationally-approved research ethics bodies in Uganda and Tanzania, and Oxford Tropical Research Ethics Committee, UK. We will register the trial on an independent study registry (www.clinicaltrials.gov). The study will be conducted according to ICH GCP guidelines and the Declaration of Helsinki. Findings from other studies with implications for the on-going running of the trial will be discussed by the trial investigators with the TSC and DSMB to support best practices throughout the study.

17.1. Human Subjects

17.1.1. Risks

The investigational drugs that will be administered in this trial are already widely used and are licensed treatments in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania. The most common side effects include; skin rash, abdominal discomfort, headache, loss of appetite, nausea and vomiting. Penicillins (benzyl penicillin or ampicillin and the amoxicillin component of amoxicillin-clavulanic acid) and cephalosporins can cause anaphylactic reactions in those allergic to them. We will inquire about any history of drug allergies prior to enrolment.

The procedures of intravenous cannula insertion for the administration of injectable antibiotics and intravenous fluid and of nasogastric tube insertion are both associated with transient discomfort during the procedure. Intravenous cannula insertion carries the additional risks of failure of the procedure, bruising at the cannula site, extravasation of the cannula or infection introduced via the cannula. Nasogastric tube insertion carries the additional risks of tube misplacement or subsequent displacement. Both of these procedures and subsequent administration of intravenous treatments and testing for nasogastric tube placement within the stomach will be done by experienced nurses according to the relevant study SOPs and every effort will be made to minimise discomfort and complications.

Collection of nasopharyngeal samples carries minimal risk of serious adverse consequences but is associated with mild discomfort, something that will be explained to the caregivers. Similarly, no risk is anticipated from performing chest radiography as part of this study. Specific consent will be requested prior to collection of nasopharyngeal samples and chest radiographs.

Emergency care will take precedence over all study procedures. Study procedures that may delay the safe management of study participants during emergencies, such as insertion of nasogastric tubes for feeding will be deferred until it is deemed safe. In any situation in which the paediatrician feels it is in the best interest of the child not to randomise or not to follow protocol this will be permissible, and the data recorded for appropriate analyses.

17.1.2. Benefits to the Patients and Community as a Whole

All children enrolled in the study will benefit from close daily monitoring for clinical deterioration and severe adverse effects of the study treatments by a study specific clinician in addition to the hospital team providing routine care. If detected, such events will result in

immediate appropriate action. Staff attending to the study participants will benefit from training on case management of childhood pneumonia which will contribute towards overall improvement of patient care.

Costs of study treatments, investigations performed for research purposes (processing of nasopharyngeal swab samples and chest radiographs) that are available within the study hospital will be paid for by the study. The study contributes to knowledge informing the appropriate use of antimicrobials, thus benefitting the whole community.

17.1.3. Confidentiality

On admission/enrolment, participants are issued with a unique identifying number. All clinical data will be held confidentially and personal identifiers will be removed before analysis and presentation of the results.

17.1.4. Informed Consent

Informed consent will be sought from the caregivers of all eligible participants before recruitment into the study. Where it is felt that the consenting process may delay administration of emergency care, the study clinician will seek deferred consent using an approach that has previously been successfully implemented in a large clinical trial on emergency fluid resuscitation in African children (28,38). In this procedure, the process of gaining consent is regarded as continuous with the caregiver taken through a short verbal assent process at the point of enrolment, followed by written informed consent once the patient is stabilised. Caregivers of study participants will be adequately informed of conditions of participation in all aspects of the study, including their right to decline to undergo study procedures or withdraw from the study completely without penalty. Counselling will be offered for caregivers by the study teams as part of a continuous informed consent process. The presence of a study specific clinician at each site will ensure those enrolled can receive information throughout admission and have questions answered. Telephone follow up will also enquire whether caregivers have any questions about the trial or their child's illness. Clinical and nursing staff will be trained on providing information and administering the consent procedure, following a standard operating procedure using didactic learning and role play.

17.1.5. Reimbursement

A reimbursement allowance to cover out of pocket expenses associated with participation will be provided at each scheduled visit, based on KEMRI Wellcome Trust Research Programme Guidelines for Study Benefits and Out-of-Pocket Expenses (approximately 650 KSH, 6.50 USD or 5 GBP dependent on duration and distance of travel).

17.2. Community Engagement

Through KWTRP's existing strategies, we will work to ensure clear mutual understanding is achieved regarding the study between the study team and community members. This will primarily target the hospital staff, and the surrounding communities through the county health management teams serving participating sites. Using a range of communication tools delivered in appropriate forums throughout the trial, the goals of the community engagement for this study will focus on enhancing ethical aspects of our research, ensuring understanding of the research process, and providing feedback that will ultimately facilitate adoption of the research findings into local, national and international policy.

Clinicians and nurses practising at most of the study sites and senior technical government officials in the Kenya Ministry of Health have been involved in discussions on the study from the stage of conceptualization. The respective study sites have expressed interest in participation in the study. Members of the Kenya Paediatric Association have also been engaged on the proposed study during recent scientific meetings. We will continue to engage key stakeholders during the study, including hospital staff providing care in the study hospitals through scheduled meetings, seminars and written briefs to further support communication of information on the study to caregivers, increase the knowledge of staff on the proposed study and enhance institutional capacity for the management of pneumonia.

18. DATA SHARING

Upon publication of the primary study findings, data requests will be considered by applying to the Data Governance Committee at CGMR-C Kilifi who will manage the process and ensure that appropriate ethical approval is in place and consent has been obtained for uses outside those given in this protocol. Explanation of this eventuality will be included in the participant information and consent form.

19. ARCHIVING AND RECORD RETENTION

The investigator will keep key trial documents for at least five years after the completion or discontinuation of the trial. Source documents will be retained for a minimum of 2 years from the end of the study in the institution's archive. CRFs will be retained for at least five years.

20. FINANCING AND INSURANCE

20.1. Budget

Item	Kshs	USD
<i>(a) Salaries and other disbursements</i>	150,052,110	1,500,521.10
<i>(b) Patient costs</i>	2,288,000	22,880.00
<i>(c) Equipment</i>	5,655,260	56,552.60
<i>(d) Supplies (study drugs, clinical consumables, microbiology, radiology)</i>	44,731,830	447,318.30
<i>(e) Travel and accommodation</i>	15,241,070	152,410.70
<i>(f) Public engagement</i>	5,530,850	55,308.50
<i>(g) Trial monitoring</i>	6,655,610	66,556.10
Total	230,154,730	2,301,547.30

20.2. Justification of the Budget

The proposed budget provides for full time positions for the principal investigator, a research medical officer, a trial manager, a data manager, and a trial monitor. We will hire 12 data clerks (one at each site) and 12 study clinical officers (one at each site). Other expenses include costs for reimbursement of patients for return hospital visits, purchase of computers, study supplies including all study treatments and consumables, and costs for undertaking microbiological tests and chest radiographs. Travel and accommodation costs cater for local and international trips

by investigators to sites for training, supervision, and meetings. A budget for public engagement will facilitate the design and distribution of communication materials and hosting of annual activities to commemorate World Pneumonia Day. A budget for trial monitoring by the KWTRP Clinical Trials Facility will support site initiation visits, scheduled site visits to each site every six months and a close out visits with allowance for additional visits as required.

20.3. Insurance

The study will be indemnified by the University of Oxford. The study clinicians who are involved with trial procedures have professional indemnity insurance.

21. TRIAL MANAGEMENT

21.1. Sponsor

The trial sponsor is the University of Oxford. The sponsor will be responsible for ensuring appropriate arrangements are in place for the initiation, management and financing of the trial, the trial is conducted to a high scientific quality and the rights of participants are protected.

21.2. Trial steering and safety monitoring committees

A trial steering committee (TSC) will be appointed to oversee the running of the trial, chaired by Prof. Richard Lilford (University of Warwick, Coventry, UK). Independent members are Dr Isaac Tsikhutsu (Kenya Medical Research Institute/Walter Reed Project, Kericho, Kenya), Dr Peter Waiswa (Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda), Dr Festus Kalokola (Dar es Sallam, Tanzania), and Dr. Jane Crawley (University of Oxford, Oxford, UK). The TSC will meet formally face-to-face at least annually and more frequently if necessary.

A data safety and monitoring board (DSMB) will be convened. The focus of the DSMB is safety, the overall integrity of the study, and its continued relevance and ability to answer the primary objective. Interim unblinded analyses will be conducted by the DSMB. A recommendation to the sponsor to discontinue recruitment, in all patients or in selected subgroups, may be made by the TSC on advice from the DSMB if the data provide proof beyond reasonable doubt that one of the treatment arms is better in terms of the primary outcome or safety guided by the Haybittle–Peto boundary (53,54).

22. TRAINING AND SETTING UP

All hospital staff attending to study patients will undergo training on the WHO inpatient case management guidelines for severe pneumonia. This will be followed by study-specific training. Staff at all sites will be trained on the background to the trial, scientific and ethical aspects of clinical research and trials, ICH GCP, data collection, communication, consenting procedures and SOPs for direct clinical care.

23. REPORTING, DISSEMINATION AND NOTIFICATION OF RESULTS

This study will be undertaken with the medical and nursing unit staff and the hospital consultants, who have been involved in its design and will be essential in its implementation. The study findings will not be shared directly with the caregivers of individual study participants. However, information arising from the study will be fed back through hospital-wide meetings. Results of the trial will be also shared at Ministry of Health stakeholder meetings, at the annual national paediatric association conferences in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania, at advocacy events such as the annual activities to commemorate World Pneumonia Day, and international scientific meetings. Manuscripts developed from the study findings will be submitted for publication in appropriate peer-reviewed journals.

24. REFERENCES

1. Liu L, Oza S, Hogan D, Chu Y, Perin J, Zhu J, et al. Global, regional, and national causes of under-5 mortality in 2000–15: an updated systematic analysis with implications for the Sustainable Development Goals. *Lancet*. 2016;388(10063):3027–35.
2. Webb C, Ngama M, Ngatia A, Shebbe M, Morpeth S, Mwarumba S, et al. Treatment Failure Among Kenyan Children With Severe Pneumonia—A Cohort Study. *Pediatr Infect Dis J*. 2012;
3. Agweyu A, Kibore M, Digolo L, Kosgei C, Maina V, Mugane S, et al. Prevalence and correlates of treatment failure among Kenyan children hospitalised with severe community-acquired pneumonia: a prospective study of the clinical effectiveness of WHO pneumonia case management guidelines. *Trop Med Int Heal* [Internet]. 2014;19(11):1310–20. Available from: <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/tmi.12368>
4. Agweyu A, Lilford RJ, English M, Irimu G, Ayieko P, Akech S, et al. Appropriateness of clinical severity classification of new WHO childhood pneumonia guidance: a multi-hospital, retrospective, cohort study. *Lancet Glob Heal*. 2018;6(1):e74–83.
5. World Health Organization. *Pocket Book of Hospital Care for Children: Guidelines for the Management of Common Childhood Illnesses*. Guidelines for the management of common illnesses. 2013.
6. Scott JAG, English M. What are the implications for childhood pneumonia of successfully introducing Hib and pneumococcal vaccines in developing countries? *PLoS Medicine*. 2008.
7. Adegbola RA, Levine OS. Rationale and expectations of the Pneumonia Etiology Research for Child Health (PERCH) study. *Expert Review of Respiratory Medicine*. 2011.
8. Mutinda CM, Onyango FE, Maleche-Obimbo E, Kumar R, Wamalwa D, Were F, et al. ADHERENCE TO PNEUMONIA GUIDELINES FOR CHILDREN 2 - 59 MONTHS AT GARRISA PROVINCIAL GENERAL HOSPITAL. *East Afr Med J*. 2014;
9. Tsolia MN, Psarras S, Bossios a, Audi H, Paldanius M, Gourgiotis D, et al. Etiology of Community-Acquired Pneumonia in Hospitalized School-Age Children : Evidence for High Prevalence of Viral Infections. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2004;
10. Hammitt LL, Kazungu S, Morpeth SC, Gibson DG, Mvera B, Brent AJ, et al. A

- preliminary study of pneumonia etiology among hospitalized children in Kenya. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2012;
11. Gilani Z, Kwong YD, Levine OS, Deloria-Knoll M, Scott JAG, O'Brien KL, et al. A literature review and survey of childhood pneumonia etiology studies: 2000-2010. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2012.
 12. PERCH Study Group. Aetiology of Childhood Pneumonia in Developing Countries. 11th Int Symposium Pneumococci Pneumococcal Dis (ISPPD 2018). 2018;
 13. Bigogo GM, Breiman RF, Feikin DR, Audi AO, Aura B, Cosmas L, et al. Epidemiology of respiratory syncytial virus infection in rural and urban Kenya. *J Infect Dis*. 2013;
 14. Emukule GO, Khagayi S, McMorro ML, Ochola R, Otieno N, Widdowson MA, et al. The burden of influenza and rsv among inpatients and outpatients in rural western Kenya, 2009-2012. *PLoS One*. 2014;
 15. Nokes DJ, Ngama M, Bett A, Abwao J, Munywoki P, English M, et al. Incidence and Severity of Respiratory Syncytial Virus Pneumonia in Rural Kenyan Children Identified through Hospital Surveillance. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2009;
 16. Reddy EA, Shaw A V., Crump JA. Community-acquired bloodstream infections in Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2010.
 17. Church J, Maitland K. Invasive bacterial co-infection in African children with *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria: A systematic review. *BMC Med*. 2014;
 18. English M, Punt J, Mwangi I, McHugh K, Marsh K. Clinical overlap between malaria and severe pneumonia in Africa children in hospital. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg*. 1996;
 19. Bassat Q, Machevo S, O'Callaghan-Gordo C, Sigaúque B, Morais L, Díez-Padrisa N, et al. Distinguishing malaria from severe pneumonia among hospitalized children who fulfilled integrated management of childhood illness criteria for both diseases: A hospital-based study in Mozambique. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2011;
 20. Ayieko P, Ogero M, Makone B, Julius T, Mbevi G, Nyachiro W, et al. Characteristics of admissions and variations in the use of basic investigations, treatments and outcomes in Kenyan hospitals within a new Clinical Information Network. *Arch Dis Child*. 2016;101(3).
 21. Bergogne-Berezin E. Pharmacokinetics of antibiotics in respiratory secretions. *JE P*,

- editor. New York, NY: Raven Press; 1988.
22. Harris, M., Clark, J., Coote, N., et al. British Thoracic Society guidelines for the management of community acquired pneumonia in children: Update 2011. *Thorax*. 2011;
 23. Dancer SJ. The problem with cephalosporins. *J Antimicrob Chemother*. 2001;
 24. Urbánek K, Kolář M, Lovečková Y, Strojil J, Šantavá L. Influence of third-generation cephalosporin utilization on the occurrence of ESBL-positive *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains. *J Clin Pharm Ther*. 2007;
 25. Lassi ZS, Das JK, Haider SW, Salam RA, Qazi SA, Bhutta ZA. Systematic review on antibiotic therapy for pneumonia in children between 2 and 59 months of age. *Archives of Disease in Childhood*. 2014.
 26. Bansal A, Singhi SC, Jayashree M. Penicillin and gentamicin therapy vs amoxicillin/clavulanate in severe hypoxemic pneumonia. *Indian J Pediatr*. 2006;
 27. Cetinkaya F, Gogremis A, Kutluk G. Comparison of two antibiotic regimens in the empirical treatment of severe childhood pneumonia. *Indian J Pediatr*. 2004;
 28. Maitland K, Kiguli S, Opoka RO, Engoru C, Olupot-Olupot P, Akech SO, et al. Mortality after Fluid Bolus in African Children with Severe Infection. *N Engl J Med*. 2011;
 29. van Someren V, Linnett SJ, Stothers JK, Sullivan PG. An investigation into the benefits of resiting nasogastric feeding tubes. *Pediatrics*. 1984;
 30. Fontaine E, Müller MJ. Adaptive alterations in metabolism: Practical consequences on energy requirements in the severely ill patient. *Curr Opin Clin Nutr Metab Care*. 2011;
 31. Kinsky MP, Milner SM, Button B, Dubick MA, Kramer GC. Resuscitation of severe thermal injury with hypertonic saline dextran: Effects on peripheral and visceral edema in sheep. *J Trauma - Inj Infect Crit Care*. 2000;
 32. Oakley E, Borland M, Neutze J, Acworth J, Krieser D, Dalziel S, et al. Nasogastric hydration versus intravenous hydration for infants with bronchiolitis: A randomised trial. *Lancet Respir Med*. 2013;
 33. Reintam Blaser A, Starkopf J, Alhazzani W, Berger MM, Casaer MP, Deane AM, et al. Early enteral nutrition in critically ill patients: ESICM clinical practice guidelines. *Intensive Care Medicine*. 2017.
 34. Molyneux EM, Dube Q, Banda F, Chiume M, Singini I, Mallewa M, et al. The

- Treatment of Possible Severe Infection in Infants: An Open Randomized Safety Trial of Parenteral Benzylpenicillin and Gentamicin Versus Ceftriaxone in Infants <60 days of Age in Malawi. *Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal*. 2017;
35. Agweyu A, Opiyo N, English M. Experience developing national evidence-based clinical guidelines for childhood pneumonia in a low-income setting - making the GRADE? *BMC Pediatr*. 2012;12.
 36. Edmond K, Scott S, Korczak V, Ward C, Sanderson C, Theodoratou E, et al. Long term sequelae from childhood pneumonia; systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One*. 2012;
 37. Rhodes A, Evans LE, Alhazzani W, Levy MM, Antonelli M, Ferrer R, et al. Surviving Sepsis Campaign. *Crit Care Med*. 2017;
 38. Maitland K, Molyneux S, Boga M, Kiguli S, Lang T. Use of deferred consent for severely ill children in a multi-centre phase III trial. *Trials*. 2011;
 39. Annane D, Sébille V, Charpentier C, Bollaert P-E, François B, Korach J-M, et al. Effect of treatment with low doses of hydrocortisone and fludrocortisone on mortality in patients with septic shock. *JAMA*. 2002;
 40. Harvey S, Harrison DA, Singer M, Ashcroft J, Jones CM, Elbourne D, et al. Assessment of the clinical effectiveness of pulmonary artery catheters in management of patients in intensive care (PAC-Man): A randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2005;
 41. Marshall LF, Maas AIR, Marshall SB, Bricolo A, Fearnside M, Iannotti F, et al. A multicenter trial on the efficacy of using tirilazad mesylate in cases of head injury. *J Neurosurg*. 1998;
 42. Cherian T, Mulholland EK, Carlin JB, Ostensen H, Amin R, De Campo M, et al. Standardized interpretation of paediatric chest radiographs for the diagnosis of pneumonia in epidemiological studies. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2005;
 43. Hammitt LL, Kazungu S, Welch S, Bett A, Onyango CO, Gunson RN, et al. Added value of an oropharyngeal swab in detection of viruses in children hospitalized with lower respiratory tract infection. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2011;
 44. Kamau E, Agoti CN, Lewa CS, Oketch J, Owor BE, Otieno GP, et al. Recent sequence variation in probe binding site affected detection of respiratory syncytial virus group B by real-time RT-PCR. *J Clin Virol*. 2017;
 45. Agoti CN, Otieno JR, Ngama M, Mwihuri AG, Medley GF, Cane PA, et al. Successive

- Respiratory Syncytial Virus Epidemics in Local Populations Arise from Multiple Variant Introductions, Providing Insights into Virus Persistence. *J Virol.* 2015;
46. Agoti CN, Otieno JR, Munywoki PK, Mwhuri AG, Cane PA, Nokes DJ, et al. Local Evolutionary Patterns of Human Respiratory Syncytial Virus Derived from Whole-Genome Sequencing. *J Virol.* 2015;
47. Agoti CN, Mayieka LM, Otieno JR, Ahmed JA, Fields BS, Waiboci LW, et al. Examining strain diversity and phylogeography in relation to an unusual epidemic pattern of respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) in a long-term refugee camp in Kenya. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2014;
48. Agweyu A, Gathara D, Oliwa J, Muinga N, Edwards T, Allen E, et al. Oral amoxicillin versus benzyl penicillin for severe pneumonia among Kenyan children: A pragmatic randomized controlled noninferiority trial. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2015;60(8).
49. Group ACT. Division of AIDS table for grading the severity of adult and pediatric adverse events. ... *Allergy Infect Dis Div AIDS.* 2004;
50. Harris PA, Taylor R, Thielke R, Payne J, Gonzalez N, Conde JG. Research electronic data capture (REDCap)-A metadata-driven methodology and workflow process for providing translational research informatics support. *J Biomed Inform.* 2009;42(2):377–81.
51. Lwanga S.K., Lemeshow S. Sample size determination in health studies A practice manual. World Health Organization. 1991.
52. Fancourt N, Knoll MD, Baggett HC, Brooks WA, Feikin DR, Hammitt LL, et al. Chest radiograph findings in childhood pneumonia cases from the multisite PERCH study. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2017;
53. Peto R, Pike MC, Armitage P, Breslow NE, Cox DR, Howard S V., et al. Design and analysis of randomized clinical trials requiring prolonged observation of each patient. I. Introduction and design. *Br J Cancer.* 1976;
54. Haybittle JL. Repeated assessment of results in clinical trials of cancer treatment. *Br J Radiol.* 1971;

25. APPENDICES

25.1. Role of each Investigator

	Study design and development	Community /public engagement	Training	Data Management	Clinical care	Data and sample collection	Data Analysis	Report writing
Ambrose Agweyu	•	•	•	•	•	•		•
Mike English	•	•	•	•	•	•		•
Elizabeth Maleche Obimbo	•	•	•		•	•		•
Elizabeth Allen	•			•			•	•
Adolfine Hokororo	•	•	•	•	•	•		•
Emmanuel Tenywa	•	•	•	•	•	•		•